

The principle of cascade utilization in the processing of coffee silverskin

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The cascade utilization involves the sequential multi-stage processing of a bioresource to extract target components at each stage. Coffee silverskin (CS), a lignocellulosic waste product from coffee roasting [1], was used as a carbon source for cultivating the xylophilic basidiomycete *Trametes* sp., an enzyme producer. Following filtration and enzyme purification, the process yielded two main by-products: spent medium (SM), which contains a complex of micro- and macroelements (Table) and is suitable for recycling, and biomass (approx. 5%) consisting of mycelium and residual CS.

Table. Composition of the initial nutrient medium and spent medium

Sample	N-NH ₄ ⁺	SO ₄ ²⁻	PO ₄ ³⁻	mg/dm ³				μg/dm ³	
				F ⁻	Ca	Mg	K	Zn	Al
INM*	62±12	1440	540	0,84±0,21	31±5	52±8	250±40	1150±230	19±6
SM	47±9	960±120	420±80	0,53±0,13	30±5	41±6	200±30	780±160	11±4

*Note: INM – initial nutrient medium

Figure. Appearance of the mycelium-based biocomposite

Sawdust and CS-based lignocellulosic substrate ensured effective mycelial colonization, as confirmed by complete surface coverage and dense internal growth of the biocomposite (Figure). The biocomposite exhibited high hygroscopicity due to its porous structure and the hydrophilic properties of the chitin-glucan complex. The material retained its structural integrity, and subsequent drying demonstrated resistance to cyclic moisture exposure. The density of the biocomposite was found to depend on the substrate composition and processing methods; pressed fine-disperse substrates achieved a density of 0.022–0.030 g/cm³, comparable to expanded polystyrene, which makes them promising for use in lightweight structures.

Thus, the cascade utilization of CS contributes to waste reduction, a minimized environmental footprint, enhanced economic efficiency of bioresource use, as well as job creation and strengthened energy security.

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References

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